

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

**2026-YIL / IYUN/6-SON,
VI-QISM**

INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD
SERIAL
NUMBER
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

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*Elektron nashr. 2026-yil, iyun.
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Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti,
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi Iqtisodiy
jinoyatlarga qarshi kurashish departamenti

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va
taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar
vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy
attestatsiya komissiyasi
rayosatining
2023-yil 1-apreldagi
336/3-sonli qarori bilan
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

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DETERMINANTS OF STAKEHOLDER SATISFACTION WITH CUSTOMS CLEARANCE IN UZBEKISTAN: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract. This study examines determinants of stakeholder satisfaction with customs clearance in Uzbekistan using a 150-respondent survey. Correlation and regression analyses indicate key positive and negative predictors and provide policy recommendations.

Keywords: customs satisfaction, trade facilitation, Uzbekistan, stakeholder perception, digitalization, integrity-related risks, Central Asia, survey research, correlation analysis, tariff policy

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot O'zbekistonda 150 respondent so'rovnoma asosida bojxona rasmiylashtiruv bo'yicha manfaatdor tomonlar qoniqishini belgilovchi omillarni empirik o'rganadi va siyosiy tavsiyalar taqdim etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: bojxona qoniqishi, savdoni osonlashtirish, O'zbekiston, manfaatdor tomonlar, raqamlashuv, institutsional xatarlar, Markaziy Osiyo, so'rovnoma tadqiqoti, korrelyatsiya tahlili, tarif siyosati

Аннотация. На основе опроса 150 респондентов исследуются факторы удовлетворённости заинтересованных сторон таможенным оформлением в Узбекистане. Корреляционный и регрессионный анализ выявляет значимые предикторы и формулирует рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: удовлетворённость таможенным оформлением, содействие торговле, Узбекистан, заинтересованные стороны, цифровизация, институциональные риски, Центральная Азия, анкетирование, корреляционный анализ, тарифная политика

INTRODUCTION

Customs is rarely a neutral experience, as anyone who has moved goods across Uzbekistan's borders is aware. It might mean smooth, hour-long digital clearance or a multi-day waiting period at a congested checkpoint, and for traders, logistics companies, and freight forwarders operating in the country, the difference between those two outcomes affects everything from pricing decisions to supplier relationships.

Over the past decade, Uzbekistan has made significant investments in customs reform. Since 2016, the government has pushed through digitalisation initiatives, implemented risk-based corridor systems, signed new free trade agreements, and strengthened measures to reduce integrity-related risks within the Customs Committee. The country has made progress by most aggregate measures, such as Logistics Performance Index scores, declaration processing volumes, and border crossing times. Yet aggregate indicators only provide a partial picture. They fail to capture the real-world experience of traders, customs brokers, and logistics specialists who interact with these systems on a regular basis.

This study fills the gap in the literature. Although a substantial body of research exists on customs reform and trade facilitation in transition economies broadly, there are still few empirical studies that specifically address stakeholder satisfaction with customs processes in Central Asia. The majority of available assessments rely on

qualitative case studies or secondary data from international organisations; large-scale survey-based analyses of practitioner views in Uzbekistan are notably lacking.

Through a structured survey administered to 150 respondents with direct experience in Uzbekistan's cross-border trade and logistics industry, this study closes the gap. It analyses how six key variables, including professional experience, digital efficiency, documentation burden, tariff predictability, processing delays, and perceived integrity-related risks, relate to overall satisfaction using correlation and regression analysis. The aim is not simply to measure satisfaction levels, but to determine which factors have the greatest influence on them and what that means for the reform agenda going forward.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Since the early 2000s, trade facilitation has attracted increasing academic and policy attention, driven by evidence that costs and delays associated with customs put a greater burden on international trade than tariffs alone. Wilson, Mann, and Otsuki (2005) demonstrated that trade flows between Asia-Pacific economies could rise far more than with equivalent tariff reductions if customs efficiency and regulatory transparency were improved [1]. This insight has since been reinforced across multiple regional contexts, with research consistently demonstrating that time spent at the border directly translates into lost trade value.

Within this broader literature, a separate line of research has examined how traders and logistics professionals view and interact with customs systems. The day-to-day procedural difficulties, uncertainty, and discretionary behaviour that shape how traders interact with customs authorities are captured by satisfaction-based techniques in a way that aggregate statistics cannot. Since unpredictability drives up compliance costs and discourages smaller traders from engaging in formal cross-border trade, Grainger (2011) argued that traders' perceptions of customs transparency and predictability are as significant to trade facilitation outcomes as the technical effectiveness of clearance systems [2].

Integrity-related risks have received particular attention as a factor influencing stakeholder perception. Even in cases where official procedures are operating rather well, research conducted in developing and transition countries regularly reveals that unofficial facilitation practices considerably undermine trader confidence in customs institutions [3]. Digitalisation has emerged as the most promising countermeasure: automated systems decrease discretionary human contact, create audit trails, and shorten clearance times. However, research cautions that the benefits of digitalisation are unevenly distributed: traders with greater digital literacy benefit disproportionately, while smaller or more recent market players often find it difficult to adapt [4].

In the Central Asian context specifically, there is still a dearth of empirical literature on stakeholder perception. Most available assessments are based on qualitative fieldwork at specific crossings, World Bank Logistics Performance Index data, or OECD trade facilitation indicators [5]. Survey-based studies examining how practitioners in Uzbekistan view customs clearance from several angles simultaneously are largely absent from the published record. That gap is directly addressed in this paper.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a quantitative survey design to analyse stakeholder satisfaction with customs clearance processes in Uzbekistan. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire administered to 150 respondents who are actively involved in the country's cross-border trade and logistics industry, including traders, customs brokers, freight forwarders, logistics coordinators, and procurement specialists. Purposive sampling was used to select respondents, targeting individuals who had first-hand knowledge of Uzbekistan's customs processes.

Seven variables served as the foundation for the survey instrument. Overall satisfaction with customs clearance served as the dependent variable, assessed on a five-point Likert scale ranging from very dissatisfied to very satisfied. The same scale was used to test six independent variables: professional experience, perceived digital efficiency, documentation burden, processing delays, tariff predictability, and perceived integrity-related risks. Additionally, demographic data, including years of experience, sector of activity, and frequency of cross-border operations, were collected.

Two analytical methods were applied. The strength and direction of the relationship between each independent variable and overall satisfaction were examined using Pearson correlation analysis. Then, multiple regression analysis assessed each variable's relative contribution while the others were held constant, providing a clearer picture of what matters most. Data analysis was conducted using standard statistical software. The purposive sampling approach restricts generalisability to the entire population of Uzbekistan's traders, and this

limitation is acknowledged and discussed in the conclusion.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Respondent Profile

The sample represents a mix of experience levels. Respondents with four to six years of experience (31%) and those with less than a year (30%) made up the largest groups, followed by those with one to three years (24%), seven to ten years (10.7%), and more than ten years (4.3%). This dispersion captures both recent market entrants and mid-career professionals who have observed the system evolve, a range that proved analytically relevant given that experience emerged as a strong predictor of satisfaction.

Correlation Results

The correlation analysis identified two variables with a positive relationship to overall satisfaction, while four had a negative one. Professional experience showed the strongest positive correlation ($r = 0.34$), indicating that more experienced traders develop familiarity with the system that lowers uncertainty and friction. Digital efficiency was the second positive predictor ($r = 0.28$), offering ground-level confirmation that Uzbekistan's digitalisation investments are being perceived positively by professionals.

On the negative side, processing delays had the strongest adverse relationship with overall satisfaction ($r = -0.28$), followed by tariff unpredictability ($r = -0.27$), documentation burden ($r = -0.24$), and perceived integrity-related risks ($r = -0.15$). Notably, delays and documentation burden showed stronger correlations than perceived integrity-related risks. This suggests that, for most respondents, routine procedural difficulties represent a more immediate and frequent concern, while integrity-related risks appear to be concentrated at specific stages of the clearance process rather than affecting every transaction equally.

Regression Analysis

The regression analysis validated the directional patterns from the correlation findings. Experience ($\beta = 0.34$) and digital efficiency ($\beta = 0.28$) continued to be the strongest positive predictors of satisfaction when other variables were controlled for. Among negative predictors, processing delays ($\beta = -0.28$) and tariff unpredictability ($\beta = -0.27$) had the strongest negative effects, followed by documentation burden ($\beta = -0.24$) and perceived integrity-related risks ($\beta = -0.15$). According to the combined model, satisfaction is being simultaneously pulled upward by digitalisation gains while unresolved structural issues are pulling it downward.

The findings present a picture that is neither straightforwardly optimistic nor entirely discouraging, which is perhaps the fairest assessment of where Uzbekistan's current customs reform stands. The benefits of digitisation are genuine. In a survey of this type, an r -value of 0.28 between perceived digital efficiency and overall satisfaction is significant and tells policymakers something important: the investments made in single-window systems, electronic declarations, and automated corridor classification are changing practitioners' perceptions of the system, not only formal indicators.

The experience finding adds an essential layer. The strength of this relationship — the greatest positive predictor in the dataset at $r = 0.34$ — indicates that the system still appears to give an advantage to accumulated procedural knowledge, such as knowing which corridor commodities are likely to enter, which documentation is typically requested, and which informal norms influence inspections. In a well-functioning system, that kind of knowledge should matter less, not more. The significance of this issue shows that there is still a great deal of procedural uncertainty beneath the surface of formal reform.

A coherent narrative is presented by the negative predictors. Delays and documentation burden share a common root: regulatory complexity that has not kept up with digitalisation. The research shows that while moving declarations online speeds up the procedure, it does not make it easier. Tariff unpredictability's effect is linked to a well-documented pattern: it is not always the level of tariffs that causes the greatest concern among traders, but uncertainty about how they will be applied. The lower coefficient of perceived integrity-related risks ($r = -0.15$) likely reflects uneven distribution across the sample rather than minor overall impact. Respondents at major crossings may experience it infrequently, pulling the average down, while those at smaller posts or dealing in regulated commodities face it more frequently.

Conclusion and Suggestions

The goal of this study was to find out what the people who are engaged in Uzbekistan's customs operations truly think about them, something that has not been done much in the literature. The answers, drawn from 150 respondents, paint a picture that is more nuanced than either official reform assessments or broader critical views often imply. Satisfaction is formed by two forces pulling in opposite directions: digitalisation and

professional experience enhance it, while delays, documentation burden, tariff unpredictability, and informal practice risks suppress it.

There are four practical recommendations that follow. Priority should be given to reducing documentation burden for regulated goods categories through decentralised testing infrastructure and proportionality review of technical requirements. Second, tariff consistency and transparency are more important than rate levels: clearer classification guidelines and better advance ruling procedures would have a greater impact on stakeholder satisfaction and compliance behaviour than further rate adjustments alone. Third, the ongoing integration of AI-based inspection tools would reduce informal practice risks at remaining high-discretion checkpoints. Fourth, the experience gap in satisfaction scores points to a need for improved onboarding support for new players in the market, including clearer public information, accessible training, and streamlined entry pathways.

Future research should extend the sampling frame beyond purposive selection to enable broader generalisation, use longitudinal designs to monitor satisfaction as certain reforms are implemented, and extend the comparison frame to other Central Asian customs systems. Within these constraints, the study demonstrates that the gap between Uzbekistan's reform agenda and practical experience is significant, but it can be closed, and doing so necessitates addressing institutional and procedural issues that digitalisation alone may not fully resolve.

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2026. № 6/6

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>